

PMI Periodical

NAU NORTHERN ARIZONA UNIVERSITY

Hi Everyone,

Greetings from Flagstaff! We are pleased to send you this Fall 2024 edition of the PMI Periodical.

In this edition we are delighted to introduce you to our newest faculty member, Dr. Kelly Speer. Kelly has hit the ground running and is already doing very exciting research and contributing to the teaching mission of NAU. She's a great fit for PMI and NAU and we are thrilled to have her on our team.

We also provide details on one of our newest initiatives – Undergrad Bootcamp. We have trained hundreds of undergraduate researchers over the years and our undergraduate program, headed by Dr. Dawn Birdsell, is very highly regarded at NAU. In an effort to be able to train even more undergraduate students, Dawn developed Undergraduate Bootcamp to provide intensive trainings to new students in basic laboratory skills. Our goal is to free individual PMI faculty from many of these initial trainings so we can onboard and train even more students!

Dr. Dan Kollath prepared a great summary of project that PMI is working on with ASU and UA to better understand *Coccidioides posadasii* (the fungus that causes Valley Fever) in Arizona. This tri-university endeavor is bringing together diverse experts across the state to try and better understand the ecology of *C. posadasii* in the environment, which remains poorly understood.

In October, PMI and NAU hosted – for the second year in a row – a state-wide meeting focused on Rocky Mountain spotted fever, a deadly disease that disproportionately affects Tribal communities in Arizona. It is our intention to continue to host this meeting annually at NAU in the future. We also included our annual group photo from our fall “all-hands” meeting, which is one of the few times that we are able to get all (or most) of our ~150 people together in the same place.

Finally, you may notice below that I have a new title – Executive Director of PMI. After 35 years of outstanding leadership, Dr. Paul Keim stepped down as Executive Director of PMI. But not to worry, Paul has not retired as a faculty member! He continues to teach at NAU and is as active as ever with research now that he has been freed of administrative responsibilities. I am humbled and honored to serve as the new EXD of PMI.

Happy holidays!

Dave Wagner - Executive Director of PMI

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Introducing... Kelly Speer!

Kelly Speer

Dr. Kelly Speer (she/her) is an Assistant Professor in the Department of Biological Sciences and the Pathogen & Microbiome Institute at Northern Arizona University. Speer's research leverages field-based systems and natural history collections to examine the impact of environmental change on pathogen and vector dynamics. She specifically focuses on the interactions between bats, blood-feeding arthropods, and the beneficial and pathogenic microorganisms associated with both as a model for understanding how complex natural communities respond to disturbances like habitat loss or disease emergence. Speer completed her postdoctoral research in Biodiversity Genomics and Theoretical Medicine at the National Museum of Natural History and Smithsonian Conservation Biology Institute.

She received her Ph.D. in Comparative Biology from the Richard Gilder Graduate School at the American Museum of Natural History, her M.S. in Zoology at the University of Florida, and a B.S. in Biology and B.A. in Chemistry at the University of New Mexico. Prior to joining NAU, she was an Assistant Professor in the Department of Ecology & Evolutionary Biology at the University of Michigan and Director of the Michigan Pathogen Biorepository.

Kelly Speer, PhD
Photo courtesy of Kelly Speer

Undergrad Bootcamp – Onboarding our Newest Members

Dawn Birdsell

As the Associate Director of the Training and Education Core for PMI, I oversee the undergraduate research program. Undergraduate students are the next generation workforce, and the PMI undergraduate research program is designed to provide skill-generating experiences that will position students to be more career ready in their future professions. PMI is an internationally recognized cutting-edge research institute where students can learn alongside some of the world's leading microbiologists and genomics experts who identify superbugs through DNA sequencing, track pathogens to study deadly outbreaks, and develop vaccines to prevent disease.

Currently, we have 30 actively enrolled undergrad student researchers who work around 15 - 20 hours a week all year round. Each student is a member of one of 15 different research groups. Within that home research group, students are mentored and trained to become capable researchers. This includes intense training in laboratory procedures.

For new students entering PMI, stepping into this opportunity can seem a bit daunting. To help onboard each new cohort of students and to promote comradery among them, we initiated a program called PMI Undergrad Bootcamp starting in Fall 2024. This five-part laboratory training course is designed to be supplementary to the lab training new students will receive from their home research group. Students will be introduced to the basic conceptual knowledge of research and to best practices for lab procedures. The aim is to confer in students the ability of operational excellence when working in a laboratory environment. The goals are to 1) provide more uniform basic laboratory training across all faculty groups, and 2) instill in students an understanding of universal principles behind research protocols. Success with these goals will potentially translate to decreased burden placed on home research groups for initial training, an increase in quality of research, and an increase in engagement of newly enrolled undergraduates to further expedient onboarding. Upon the completion of this course, students should feel more comfortable and confident working in a research lab.

Skill transformation of students into competent career ready professionals is the mission of NAU, PMI, and our funding agencies. This bootcamp will assist in leveling up the performance of our students to excel in the research space and position them to be highly competitive in their next career endeavors.

Undergrad Research Bootcamp

Photo courtesy of K. Ng

ABOR Grant Surrounding *Coccidioides posadasii*

Dan Kollath

The fungal pathogen *Coccidioides posadasii* is responsible for more infections than any other infectious agent in the state of Arizona. Despite this, there is a substantial lack of knowledge regarding the ecology of *Coccidioides* and how it directly relates to disease transmission. Multiple environmental parameters come into play when defining the suitable niche for these organisms (i.e. precipitation, temperature, soil chemistry, mammal presence, etc.). Few studies have analyzed the association between the presence of *Coccidioides* spp. and abiotic and biotic influences, such as animal burrows, climatic factors, and soil/air chemistry. There is even less information on how these factors influence the presence of *Coccidioides* spp. temporally. In this study, we assessed monthly soil samples from animal burrows as well as surface soil for 3 years at a single location in the metropolitan area of Phoenix, Arizona for the presence of *Coccidioides*. Collaborators in Jon Chorover's Lab at University of Arizona conducted chemical analysis of soils to identify abiotic factors that may be influencing the presence of *Coccidioides*.

Industrial Air Sampler for Valley Fever

Photo courtesy of Marieke Ramsey

Daniel Kollath Sampling

Photo courtesy of Marieke Ramsey

We also conducted weekly air sampling to identify the presence of *Coccidioides* in the ambient air through time and chemical analysis with help of our collaborators Pierre Herckes and Matthew Fraser at Arizona State University. We were able to detect the presence of *Coccidioides* in the soil every month for 2 years and are currently processing year 3, however, there were slight variations on the intensity of positive soil samples per month with March and October having the least probability of detection in the soil. The detection of *Coccidioides* in air samples showed a great deal of variation from month to month, with February and July showing the highest probability in detecting the fungus. Particulate matter 10 microns and below, collected from onsite filters, demonstrates a positive relationship with the presence of *Coccidioides* in the air with the majority of particulate matter being crustal and not coming from anthropogenic sources. We observed geographic variation in the presence of the fungus in the soil with certain burrow systems being consistently positive for the fungus every month while others are only transiently positive. Soil chemical analysis identified significantly higher inorganic nitrogen in soil from burrows systems that are consistently positive for *Coccidioides*. We were only able to detect *Coccidioides* in 0.02% of soils collected from non-animal burrows surface soils. The present study was the first of its kind to examine temporal and geographic differences in the presence of *Coccidioides* spp. in soil and air for one year at a hyper-endemic location in Arizona.

Coccidioides spp. is extremely difficult to culture directly from the soil, previous methods are time consuming with a very low success rate. Thus, there is no baseline of environmental diversity which makes performing genomic epidemiological methods impossible. The other goal of this project was to establish a culture-free DNA capture enrichment method to perform genomic analyses on *Coccidioides* without having to isolate the fungus itself. This part of the project is led by Dr. Dave Wagner and Dr. Jason Sahl. To date, the team successfully enriched a handful of different complex environmental samples to begin to establish a baseline of genetic diversity. This promising method is a “game changer” for the future of tracking the transmission of this pathogen.

This project is funded by the Arizona Board of Regents through the Translational Research Initiative Fund Regent's award.

Rocky Mountain spotted fever Progress

Johanna Salzer

On Oct 29th and 30th, 2024 NAU hosted partners for a second year in a row to discuss progress and ideas for preventing Rocky Mountain spotted fever in Arizona, a deadly tickborne disease. This was a multidisciplinary meeting with 68 attendees, including partners from CDC, Arizona Department of Health Services, academics, and eight tribal communities. The meeting focused on key prevention strategies and tangible outcomes to protect both people and animals. RMSF-impacted communities shared lessons learned through experience in community education, addressing animal wellness, and harnessing networks to improve outputs. Training sessions on pesticide safety, grant writing, and developing an RMSF prevention action plan were held in response to feedback from last year's meeting.

PMI All Hands

Deborah Martin

Friday, November 15th, 2024, PMI faculty, staff, and students gathered for the annual PMI All-Hands meeting. The purpose of the PMI annual all-hands meeting is to meet, collaborate, and recognize all faculty, staff, and students at PMI. We celebrate successes in the lab and successes of our personnel. We recognized the two students graduating in winter 2024, Hannah Finkel and Jaida Salois, and are proud of their accomplishments as student researchers in the lab.

The 2024 All Hands Meeting included a group photo, please see the photo included with the article. Even with people not able to attend, we barely fit on the stairs for our annual group photo.

Students at PMI are the foundation that we build upon as PMI continues to conduct outstanding research, working to make an impact on the world. Enjoy the photos and see if you recognize any of the faces in the group picture.

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Please Keep In Touch!

We love hearing from all of our alumni and friends! If you have news to share, please take a moment to complete the following to update us with your latest news, accomplishments and contact information.

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